

Linda Nichols
Editor

This edition begins a new journey for me and as I approach my second decade of nursing, I am honoured to be taking over the helm as Editor of the AJoN.

Thank you Vicki for your guest editorial. Change is certainly continuous and this is also true in terms of journals and publishing.

Those of you who remember the early volumes will have seen many changes over the years. In my lifetime, I have seen technology develop and I often reflect on how we managed prior to smart phones and the internet.

With this in mind I honour the early journal editors, when articles were typed and sent back and forwards via post with handwritten comments that needed to be addressed.

The internet and email has changed many things we do and whilst it is not always for the better it has certainly made this job of editor and my substantive role as an academic easier.

Now we can share articles electronically using email and platforms such as Research Gate. However, not so long ago this task was completed via posted request for reprints. Academics would have calling cards printed that they would send to authors requesting a copy of manuscripts and waiting patiently for the copy to be posted them. Now our poor library staff are pressured to find and deliver archived and obscure articles in hours, not the weeks or even months that this task once took.

We take the ability to search the internet for granted at times and often forget that this is a relatively new technology. Access to literature is now often overwhelming and perhaps it was easier in the old days when you could not be criticised for not knowing what you didn't have access to. However, like many of you I will take an electronic search engine any day over the hours I remember scanning microfiche cards.

Vicki Evans
We've come a long way....

As I approach a milestone third decade of being a Registered Nurse, everywhere around me tells me that we are surrounded by 'change' and that if you don't go with the flow, you'll be swept aside. Nursing and medicine are in continuous motion, constantly changing, formulating ways for improvement and best practice.

Some of you may remember the days of spinal surgery and the use of 'pillow packs' and log rolls for several days. Nowadays no one lies in bed. The hospital in which I work reported on the world-first vertebral artery stent. Now, stenting is hardly uncommon.

Today, the news is reporting that an Australian neurosurgeon has completed a world-first surgery removing a vertebral chordoma and successfully replacing the vertebra with a 3D-printed body part. Constant change.

So what have I learned in the seven years in the editor's role? I have learned to check and recheck, that submissions don't just come in automatically, that there are many people around to assist and that neuro nurses do great things!

In keeping with the state of constant movement, it is time to hand the editorial responsibilities over to Linda Nichols. Linda is a neuro nurse and academic from the University of Tasmania.

She was a regular provider of manuscripts for the AJoN over the years and I encourage you as members/readers to send in your manuscripts for publication. What you are doing out there makes a difference – why not tell people?

To assist Linda in her new role, I asked the question:-

What is an Editor? The Collins Dictionary describes the editor as a person who is in charge of, determines selection and revises the final content of material for publication in a newspaper, magazine, or book.

The editor's role encompasses many points including–

To find an article we now head to the internet and simply search. The internet has become an invaluable resource, it has opened up endless opportunities for our own research, be that to publish or just to find information.

This is a huge change from 20 years ago when an academic would refer to 'Current Contents', a weekly publication that would be 100s of printed pages that was organised by field (life sciences, physical sciences or humanities).

'Current Contents' was a paper data base/index, a compilation of the Tables of Contents of all the journals in the fields. From here researchers would spend hours reading and scanning for key words, reference numbers and citations. Then if you were really organised, these details were hand written on a card system. When I get frustrated with End Note I always try to take a deep breath and think of the alternatives.

With all these changes and the anticipated changes ahead I read and take on board Vicki's advice. For me this is another rewarding challenge in my neuroscience journey and I look forward to this next stage.

Cheers and thank you for all your support and guidance Vicki.

Linda

Publicising the AJoN and encouraging submissions.

Screening manuscripts and sending to the Review Team for peer comment.

Final decisions: Once peer review has been completed, the editor decides on final acceptance or rejection.

Communication: the editor is required to communicate to the ANNA Executive formally & informally as well as the Review Team and prospective authors.

Ethical dilemmas: Occasionally, the editor is asked to make decisions concerning ethical issues such as possible plagiarism or multiple submissions of the same material to other journals.

Administrative & Technical duties: The editor participates in numerous procedures essential to publication of the AJoN including the makeup and layout of each issue. Manuscripts are converted by the Editor from a Word document to a Publisher file and formatted before being sent to the printers as a PDF. Factors that must be considered include the quality and size of figures/tables and proofreading of the final version before the print-run.

All the best Linda!

Vicki

